
SPECIFIC FEATURES OF INDIVIDUAL WORK WITH PRIMARY PUPILS

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Abstract. This article discusses the specific features of individual work with primary school pupils.

Keywords: innovative technology, education, intellectual development, methodology.

INTRODUCTION. In education, the development of the personality and the realization of the student's potential are a priority task. In this regard, individual learning technologies play an important role. In it, teaching methods and methods are selected based on an individual approach to the organization of the educational process and are implemented through various educational, methodological, psychological, pedagogical and organizational management measures.

MAIN PART. As is known, the problem of personality and its uniqueness, individuality is still a controversial and interesting topic of such disciplines as general psychology, differential psychology, personality psychology. In our opinion, individuality implies a specific approach to the study of personality, expressing in content such issues as the behavioral qualities of a person, character traits and their dynamics, the higher nervous system and the features of its manifestation.

The collective nature of lessons creates competition among students, stimulates their cognitive activity, helps to develop their creative abilities, and helps to form discipline, diligence, friendship and other moral qualities. However, although lessons are conducted in a collective manner, educational and cognitive activity and the assimilation of knowledge by students include the individual characteristics of their thinking, memory, intelligence, abilities, as well as learning motives and attitudes. The question arises of taking these features into account and organizing individual work with students during the lessons.

As is known, primary school is an important stage in the development of a person's age and personality, which must guarantee a high level of education. Since the school educates children with different levels of development, and the main school cannot offer each student an individual curriculum, our teachers are looking for educational models that ensure personal development, taking into account individual psychological and intellectual abilities. Most of the technologies used in education are aimed at group teaching methods based on the same requirements, time consumption, and the amount of material studied, without taking into account the specifics of the individual psychological development of each student, which does not lead to significant results in learning. As a result, not only children with low mastery, but also very hardworking children do not like school. In the current era of advanced technologies, the ability to correctly use modern technologies in educational institutions, especially in primary grades, is gaining great importance in the effective organization of the educational process.

CONCLUSION. Today, the attention and investments made in the field of education in our Republic place great responsibility on the shoulders of today's teachers and require professional aspiration from them. Increasing the effectiveness of the use of individualized teaching technologies in primary education. Because ensuring the realization of the student's existing capabilities is a requirement of the accelerating scientific and technological progress in the modern educational process. In this regard, individualized teaching technologies play an important role. In it, teaching methods and methods are selected based on an individual approach to organizing the educational process and are implemented through various educational, methodological, psychological, pedagogical and organizational management measures. The globalization of education, the effective use of modern pedagogical and information technologies in the educational process are leading to an increase in the quality of teaching in educational institutions, especially in primary grades.

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